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STATUS OF SNSs USAGE BY UNDERGRADUATE STUDENTS

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Abstract

Use of Social Networking Sites (SNSs) is very common these days. Undergraduates are the frequent users SNSs. They are spending lots of time on internet in visiting these sites for the purpose of their higher study, searching job and other opportunities. In this study researcher wants to gain an idea regarding the current SNS usage of the undergraduate students. To estimate its use, a SNSs Usage Inventory has been constructed by the researcher. In this research, researcher has selected three different aided Degree College in NCR region affiliated to CCS University, Meerut through random cluster purposive sampling technique. Only those students were chosen as sample, which were using SNSs. On the basis of descriptive analysis it was found that both male and female students were using SNS. Undergraduate students had average level of familiarity with the features of SNS. Most of them are new users. Majority of them update their SNS profile once in a week. About 70% of Undergraduate students check their SNS account on daily basis. Mostly Undergraduate students comment on others post at least once in a week and some of them rarely comment on other's post. Most of Undergraduate students were highly active to share the post on SNSs while very less of them never shares others post. The results of the study are useful for the students, parents, Lecturers, and administration of University.

Key Words: SNSs Usage, SNS, Undergraduate students

INTRODUCTION

In the digital age, the number of social media users is increasing. Everyone's connections are increasingly moving online. According to studies, the largest numbers of people (615.9 million) are using SNSs in Asian-Pacific regionsⁱ. The craze of SNSs in India is also increasing rapidly. Out of 1,256 million Indian populations, 106 million are active social media usersⁱⁱ. Out of this figure, Face book alone is adding 16 million new users since January 2014 and it can be said that one new user is being added every second. The number of face book users in India alone is over 100 million. Simultaneously other SNSs are also growing day by day by improving their number of users. Dingra(2011)ⁱⁱⁱ in his study on social media found that India comes third when it comes to social networking and photo sharing. The reason observed behind the astonishing excessive usage of SNSs as these are easy to use and navigate, does not require advanced knowledge and experience of the internet and are made up of a wide array of different formats and topics; this means that just about anyone can connect, the basic requirement is the availability of internet(Lunden, 2013)^{iv}.

SNSs are the online platform where users allowed sharing their ideas, pictures, posts, activities, events, and interests with people in their network. This also contain category places where people belong to same field connected (such as former schoolmates or classmates, professionals etc.), and have means to connect with family and friends (usually with self-description pages), and a recommendation system linked to trust. Since the times, SNSs became popular among teenagers and university students^v. Madge, Meek, Wellens and Hooley^{vi} in their research study on first year students called Facebook as a 'social glue' that helped students to settle into their university life. Hamat, Embi and Hassan^{vii} in their nationwide survey on tertiary level students in Malaysia was not found full 100% penetration of SNSs, as they assumed initially. Students was found to spent most time on SNSs for socializing rather than learning and they did not believe that the use of SNSs was affecting their academic performance. In Indian context Bharati and Singh(2018)^{viii} found that most of higher education students use the Whatsapp followed by Facebook. all the students (UG, PG and research scholars) have accepted that the social networking websites have a greater impact on their personality. Through this paper, the researcher is trying to detect the current status of the usage of SNSs among the undergraduate students in local context and also want to check the level to which students are engrossed in different activities on SNSs.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

The main objective of this study is to know the current status and level of the use of online SNSs by the Undergraduate students of Aided Colleges.

The following research questions were used to guide the study:

- i. Who among male and female students more using SNSs?
- ii. How much they are using SNSs?
- iii. Since when they are using SNSs?
- iv. Which SNSs is popular among Undergraduate students?
- v. How much the Undergraduate students are familiar with the features of SNS?
- vi. How much time do Undergraduate students spend on the various activities on SNSs?

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The Descriptive research design and survey method has been chosen for this study.

POPULATION AND SAMPLE

The target population of this study was defined as the Undergraduate students belonging to the different Aided Degree colleges affiliated to CCS University, Meerut. First of all by using lottery technique, three Aided Degree colleges of NCR region were selected randomly, then all present SNS users Undergraduate students in the class were taken as sample from all three colleges. Overall 164 Undergraduate students were taken as a sample by Random cluster Purposive sampling.

A SNSs Usage Inventory was framed by the researcher to find the use of online SNSs by the Undergraduate students. This self-constructed SNSs Usage Inventory includes demographic details and sixteen items related to the SNSs usage of the participants. In

this study analysis was done with the help of MS Excel. The present study is limited to the Government Aided degree colleges affiliated to CCS University, Meerut only.

DATA ANALYSIS

1) Demographic Analysis–

In this research total 164 undergraduate students participated among which 43, 54 and 67 were selected from College A, B, and College C. Sample of 75 male and 89 female undergraduate students was taken from above said Colleges.

Gender	Total Number of Participants	Total Percentage (%) of Participants
Male	75	45.7
Female	89	54.3
Total	164	100

Table 1: Showing gender wise distribution of undergraduate students from Colleges A, B & C

Table1 clearly shows that 45.7 % male and 54.3% female undergraduate students participated in this study. Number of female participants is more than male.

2) Internet Usage By Undergraduate Students

After the analysis of data it was found that, 37.2 % undergraduate participants are frequent internet users while 57.9% use internet sometimes and only 4.9% use internet rarely.

3) SNSs Usage By Undergraduate Students

SNSs usage by the Undergraduate students was defined under following categories:

- i. Devices used for SNSs
 - ii. Frequency of SNS use
 - iii. Daily time spent on SNSs
 - iv. On an average time spent on SNS on each visit
 - v. Difference of time spent on SNS on week days and holidays
- i. As far as the devices for SNSs use concerned, it was found that 100% of participants use their mobile phones to access SNSs. While 34.15%, 26.83%, 17% and 12.2% participants also use their laptops, personal computer, college computer and cyber café respectively along with mobile to access their SNSs accounts. It is clearly shown in figure1.

Figure 1: Representing Devices used for SNS usage by Undergraduate students

- ii. In case of frequency of SNSs (SNS) use by undergraduate students 39.6% participants visited multiple times a day, 37.2% visited daily once, 11% visited multiple times in week and 6.7% participants visited once in a week. Although very few 5.5% students also confirmed their monthly or rarely use of SNSs.
- iii. When asked about the daily time spent on SNSs 42.68% of participants responded that they spent less than one hour, 38.4% spent 1-3 hours per day, 8.5% spent 3-5 hours per day, 4.27% spent 5-7 hours and only 3.7% Undergraduate students spent 7-9 hours per day. While 2.44% participants were there who had reported their more than 9 hours usage of SNSs daily. After analysis it was found that 6% Undergraduate students are heavy users of SNSs as they spent more than 7 hours on SNSs daily.
- iv. On a question regarding an average time spent on SNS on visiting each time in it was found that 27.44% participant spent minimum 15 min or less time, 29.9% spent around half an hour, 20.7% spent around one hour, about 12.2% spent 2 hours and 6.7% spent 3-4 hours in a single visit on SNSs each time. While a few participants i.e., 3.05% has mentioned that they use SNS for more than 4 hours at once.
- v. In response to the question total hours spent on SNS in holidays 51.4% undergraduates responded that they spent same amount of time on SNS in holidays as well as on week days, 33.54% undergraduates declared that they spent more time on SNS in holidays in comparison to week days while only 24.4% of spent less time on holidays in SNSs.

4) Time Span For Using SNSs

Only few 4.3% participants reported that they were using SNSs from last 10 years and approximately same number of Undergraduate students 4.88% were using SNS from last 7-9 years, 12.20% students were using from 4-6 years, 17.07% using since last 2-4 years, While highest number 40.85% of students SNS from last 1-2 years and 20.73% students were using SNS since last six month. This description clearly shows that very few only 9% total Undergraduate students were using SNS since last 7-10 years and most of the students are new users of SNSs.

4) Popular SNSs among Undergraduate Students

Figure 2: Representing Most Popular SNS among Undergraduate students

It is clearly shown in Figure 2 that WhatsApp was used by 100% undergraduate participant. While 85.71%, 77.14%, 57.14%, 31.43%, 21.43%, and 14.29% Undergraduate participants were using Face Book; You tube, Google +, LinkedIn, Instagram, and twitter respectively along with WhatsApp. On the other hand no participant has reported as We-chat Social Site user.

5) Familiarity with the Features of SNSs

Figure 3 clearly shows that 31.7 % Undergraduate students has find themselves very much familiar with the features of SNS, 30.5% find only a little familiar, 25.6% somewhat familiar and only 12.2% find themselves extremely familiar with the features of SNSs. They shows that every undergraduate participant who was using SNSs has different levels of familiarity with the features of SNS which vary from little to extremely.

Figure3: Representing familiarity with the features of SNS

6)Time Spent on Various Activities on SNSs

In this study various activities done on SNSs by the Undergraduates students are categorized under following heads-

- A. Updating of the SNSs profile
- B. Checking own SNSs Account
- C. Commenting on others post on SNSs
- D. Sharing of other's post on SNSs
- E. Posting own photos on SNSs
- F. Check others comment on SNS profile

Result found after analysis are as follows:

- A) On updating of the SNS profile, mixed results were found 35 % participants updates their SNSs (SNS) profiles daily ,32% updates weekly , 19.5% updates monthly , 12.8 % updates rarely while 2.4% participants never updated their SNS profile.
- B) 72% Undergraduate students check their SNSs account on daily basis ,16.5% check weekly , 7.3% monthly and a very little 4.3% Undergraduate students rarely check their SNSs account .
- C) 53.04% Undergraduate students comments on others post on the daily basis week, 22.9% comments weekly,7.3% comments monthly, 14.6% comments rarely and very few 3% undergraduate students never commented on others post on SNS.
- D) 10.4% participants share the post on SNS multiple times a day, 16.5% shares daily once, 14.6% shares post multiple times in a week, and 6.7% percent of Undergraduate students share post once in a week on SNSs. 14.6 % participants share of post on monthly basis and at the same time 5.7% Undergraduate students never shared the post. Cumulatively this shows that 43.29% students share post on SNS daily and 21.34%, Share on weekly basis.
- E) 26.2% Undergraduate students post photos on SNSs (SNS) on daily basis, 28.04% weekly ,14.6% monthly and 11.6% rarely. 19.5% participants never used this platform to post their photos.
- F) 57.3% participants' check others comment on their profile daily, 15.24% check weekly, 12.2% check monthly and only 6.7% check rarely. Although 8.5 % never check other's comment on their SNS profile. Probable reason behind not checking others comment on their SNS profile may be their rarely updating of their SNS profile.

FINDINGS AND CONCLUSION:

Findings of this study shows that all undergraduate students are using internet and they are frequent users as well. All Undergraduate students are using their mobile to visit SNSs but only few visits to cybercafé due to the availability of options to visit SNSs. After the launch of Mobile Apps of various SNSs it becomes easier to use and access these sites frequently on mobiles rather than in computers. As far as daily use of SNSs is concerned, most of Undergraduate students are using SNS multiple times of the day. It shows their continuous connectedness with others. Majority of Undergraduate students spent less than one hour on SNSs it means they are using it at minimum level. On the other hand few undergraduate students spending more than 9 hours on SNSs, which is a serious issue, as a big amount of time is being given to screen which is harmful for their eyes and body. Most of the students are new users of SNSs and started using SNS latest by last year and only a few were using SNS from more than 4 years.

Most of students were spending a very little time on SNSs i.e., 15 minutes to one hour in their single visit on SNS. It clearly shows that Undergraduate students are well regulated to utilize their time on SNS. This study revealed that majority of undergraduate students use SNSs in a balanced way in weekdays as well as in holidays. Most of the Undergraduate students has recently started using SNSs since last year very less about 20% were using SNS since more than four years. It was found that every student is using WhatsApp and most of them were also using Face Book .In this way WhatsApp and Face Book were most popular among SNSs among Undergraduate students although YouTube was also preferably used by most of them. Similar to the previous studies of Chakraborty (2012) ^{ix},and Singh and Kumar (2013)^xFace book was found most popular among all category of students .

Most of the Undergraduate students had average level of familiarity with the features of SNS. Majority of them update their SNS profile once in a week. Most of Undergraduate students check their SNS account on daily basis. Mostly Undergraduate students comment on others post at least once in a weekand very less of them rarely comment on other's post. Most of Undergraduate students were highly active to share the post on SNSs while very less of them never shares others post. Majority of students post their photos at least once in a week and very less of them didn't like todo so.

CONCLUSION

In this survey on undergraduate level students studying in aided colleges of CCS, University Meerut located near to Delhi NCR region , researcher has found that SNSs are not fully used by every undergraduate student as initially assumed. This study supported that the Undergraduate students of present era are frequently using internet and SNSs as well. They also possess average level of familiarity with the SNSs features .This gives us evidences that technology is changing its shapes day by day and becoming more users friendly. Therefore the SNS usage pattern of students should also utilized in teaching and learning process efficiently. As far as higher education students are concerned they seem interested to use these platforms and spent their lots of time over it. By keeping these points in mind, teachers can use SNSs as an effective online learning platform for higher education students. SNSs can serve as an effective medium if properly used by the teachers as an extension of their classroom activity like discussion, their reflections, surveys etc. On this platform students can remain connected with their teachers even beyond the classroom and without disturbing them in real time simultaneously teachers can guide their students after the college hours too. But this cannot be implemented completely as the penetration of the technology is not hundred percent till now. There is a need to understand the security measures associated with these online sites well and make the student aware about it too before using it.

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